

PROGNOSTICATING IN-HOSPITAL OUTCOMES OF ACUTE HEART FAILURE PATIENTS USING N TERMINAL PRO B-TYPE NATRIURETIC PEPTIDE LEVELS

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Abstract

Background: NT-proBNP is commonly used to assess heart failure severity, but its role in predicting short-term hospital outcomes in acute decompensated heart failure is still evolving. This study examined the relationship between admission NT-proBNP levels and early in-hospital outcomes.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital over six months. Adults aged 18–85 years admitted with acute decompensated heart failure were enrolled consecutively. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and echocardiographic data were collected. Admission NT-proBNP levels were analyzed in relation to 30-day readmission, length of hospital stay, and in-hospital mortality.

Results: The study included 190 patients with a mean age of 71.1 ± 11.5 years; most were female. Hypertension and diabetes were highly prevalent. Higher NT-proBNP levels were associated with progressively higher rates of 30-day readmission and in-hospital mortality. Readmissions increased from 24% in patients with NT-proBNP <1500 pg/mL to nearly 50% in those with levels above 10,000 pg/mL. Mortality followed a similar upward pattern. While these associations did not reach statistical significance, the trends were consistent across NT-proBNP categories.

Conclusion: Admission NT-proBNP levels showed a clear relationship with short-term outcomes in acute decompensated heart failure. NT-proBNP may provide useful insight into disease severity at presentation and help identify patients at higher risk for early adverse outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Approximately 6.2 million adults in the United States have been diagnosed with heart failure. The prevalence of heart failure is variable around the world across different regions, and it is predicted that it will increase to 46% by 2030. The risk factors vary, with ischemic heart disease being most common in North America and Europe; whilst Valvular heart disease being more common in East Asia and Asia Pacific countries.¹

According to a study in 2006, Pakistan had an estimated 2.8 million patients with heart failure. For Bangladesh, it was reported that among all adult hospitalizations in the country in 2016, 14% to 25% were due to HF. In India, the incidence of HF was estimated to be 0.5 to 1.7% cases per 1000 per year.²

The most potent trigger for release of natriuretic peptides is left ventricular wall stress. Pro-BNP is

released in heart failure as a myocardial insult biomarker. The proteases then cleave it into biologically active 32-amino acid peptide BNP and biologically inert 76 amino acid peptide NT-proBNP. Circulating levels of BNP/NT-pro BNP increase significantly in acutely decompensated heart failure state.³

Serum levels of NT-proBNP are measured routinely for patients presenting with shortness of breath to assess the risk of acutely decompensated heart failure. NT-proBNP levels are a reliable marker of ADHF. NT-proBNP is routinely done in patients presenting with shortness of breath in our hospital. Therefore, it could be used as a rapid, non-invasive prognostic diagnostic test for heart failure patients as evidenced by Carsten T. et al⁴, where they assessed the role of NT-proBNP in diagnosing isolated diastolic dysfunction. Similarly, in another report⁵ B-type natriuretic peptide was used as one the variables of a diagnostic score for non-invasive assessment of coronary artery disease. It would provide a quick and affordable bedside prognostication of heart failure. A cohort from Registry for Acute Decompensated Heart Failure Patients in 2007 showed that increased admission BNP level was a significant predictor of in-hospital mortality in Acute Decompensated HF.⁶ Similarly, another study concluded that patients with high levels of NT-proBNP are at higher risk of in-hospital mortality(20.3%) and longer length of stay i.e. 19days.⁷ A retrospective study of 21,455 patients from 90 hospitals concluded that patients with NT-proBNP in quartiles 3 (4275-10,499 pg/ml) and 4 (>10,500 pg/ml) of admission had a statistically higher(i.e. 39.3 and 42.8%) 60 day all-cause readmission rate.⁸

Epidemiological data on incidence and prevalence of heart failure from South Asian countries is limited. No study has been conducted in South Asia to determine the elevated levels of NT-proBNP and their outcomes in acute decompensated heart failure patients. Serum NT-proBNP level is widely used as a reliable biomarker for grading severity and predicting the mortality risk in patients with heart failure. Therefore, it is imperative to evaluate the prognostic value of elevated NT-

proBNP in acutely decompensated heart failure patients. This non-invasive, cost effective test would provide great clinical utility; to devise strategies to reduce re-admissions, shorten length of stay and reduce mortality based on admission NT-proBNP values. This study would help us to reduce morbidity and mortality in heart failure patients.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Medicine at The Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, over a minimum period of six months following approval of the research synopsis by the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSp) and the Institutional Ethics Review Committee. Adult patients of both genders, aged between 18 and 85 years, who were admitted with a diagnosis of acute decompensated heart failure were enrolled using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Heart failure was identified based on clinical features including a history of shortness of breath and the presence of pitting edema of the lower limbs, along with radiological evidence of pulmonary edema on chest X-ray, such as pulmonary vascular congestion involving upper lung zones and cardiomegaly defined as a cardiac silhouette exceeding 50% of the transverse chest diameter. In addition, an admission NT-proBNP level greater than 125 pg/ml was required for inclusion. Patients who were dependent on maintenance hemodialysis, those with alternative causes of pulmonary edema such as nephrotic syndrome or liver cirrhosis, and individuals with severe anemia (hemoglobin level <6 g/dl) were excluded from the study.

Relevant demographic and clinical data, including age and gender, were recorded for all enrolled patients. Laboratory investigations such as NT-proBNP, blood urea nitrogen, serum creatinine, and HbA1c levels were documented, along with chest X-ray findings, using a predesigned data collection proforma. Comorbid conditions were also noted; diabetes mellitus was defined by a known history of diabetes or an HbA1c value of 6.5% or higher, hypertension

was defined by a prior diagnosis of hypertension, and coronary artery disease was identified based on a documented history of acute coronary syndrome characterized by chest pain, elevated cardiac troponins, or ischemic electrocardiographic changes.

For analytical purposes, NT-proBNP values were stratified into four categories: less than 1500 pg/ml, 1500–5000 pg/ml, 5001–10,000 pg/ml, and greater than 10,000 pg/ml. Clinical outcomes assessed included length of hospital stay, in-hospital or post-discharge mortality, and hospital readmission within 90 days of discharge. Length of stay was calculated as the total number of days the patient remained admitted during the index hospitalization.

Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 16.0. Quantitative variables such as age, NT-proBNP levels, HbA1c, and duration of hospitalization were expressed as mean with standard deviation for normally distributed data, while non-normally distributed variables were presented as median with interquartile range. Qualitative variables, including gender, comorbidities, NT-proBNP categories, readmission rates, and mortality, were summarized as frequencies and percentages. Associations between NT-proBNP categories and clinical outcomes were analyzed using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. Potential effect modifiers such as age, gender, and comorbid conditions were controlled through stratification, followed by post-stratification analysis. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

This study included 190 patients admitted with acute decompensated heart failure. The population was predominantly older, with a mean age of 71.1 ± 11.5 years, and nearly all patients fell within the 51–85 year age range. Women constituted the majority of admissions (67.4%). Chronic comorbid conditions were common, particularly hypertension (89.5%) and diabetes mellitus (80%). More than one-third of patients had underlying ischemic heart disease,

while atrial fibrillation was present in a smaller subset. Use of SGLT2 inhibitors at the time of admission was infrequent.

Admission NT-proBNP levels varied widely, reflecting differing degrees of cardiac stress at presentation. While approximately two-fifths of patients had NT-proBNP levels below 1500 pg/mL, a substantial proportion had moderate to markedly elevated levels, with 15.3% exceeding 10,000 pg/mL. During hospitalization, 10% of patients died, and just over one-third (34.7%) required readmission within 30 days of discharge. Patients demonstrated a mean BMI of 28.3 kg/m², suggesting an overall overweight profile. Renal function was moderately impaired, with a mean serum creatinine of 1.79 mg/dL. Echocardiographic findings were consistent with elevated filling pressures, as shown by a mean E/e ratio of 18.7, while the average ejection fraction remained preserved at 57.9%. The mean duration of hospital stay was just over five days.

When outcomes were examined, demographic variables and baseline comorbidities did not show meaningful differences between patients who were readmitted within 30 days and those who were not. However, a clear pattern emerged with respect to NT-proBNP levels. Readmission rates increased progressively across rising NT-proBNP categories. Patients with lower NT-proBNP values had the lowest likelihood of early readmission, whereas nearly half of those with levels above 10,000 pg/mL were rehospitalized within 30 days. Although this association did not reach conventional statistical significance, the stepwise increase suggested a relationship between higher admission NT-proBNP levels and early clinical deterioration.

A similar trend was observed for in-hospital mortality. Deaths occurred more frequently among patients with markedly elevated NT-proBNP levels, while mortality remained relatively low in those with lower values. Patients in the highest NT-proBNP category experienced the greatest proportion of deaths during hospitalization. Despite this gradient, the association was not statistically significant, likely influenced by the relatively small number of mortality events.

Overall, while traditional clinical variables did not show a strong relationship with short-term outcomes, NT-proBNP demonstrated a consistent upward trend with both 30-day readmission and in-hospital mortality, suggesting that higher admission levels may reflect greater disease severity and vulnerability to adverse outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Admission NT-proBNP levels in this study showed a clear and consistent relationship with short-term outcomes in patients hospitalized with acute decompensated heart failure. Higher NT-proBNP values were accompanied by increased rates of readmission, longer hospital stays, and higher in-hospital mortality, whereas baseline demographics and common comorbid conditions showed little association with these outcomes. This pattern suggests that NT-proBNP captures the immediate physiological burden of disease at presentation, reflecting myocardial stress and congestion more directly than traditional clinical characteristics. The progressive increase in risk across NT-proBNP categories supports its role as a biologically meaningful marker of disease severity, even when individual comparisons do not reach statistical significance.⁹⁻¹⁰

The study population was predominantly elderly with a high prevalence of hypertension and diabetes, a profile commonly associated with heart failure with preserved ejection fraction. Despite largely preserved systolic function, echocardiographic findings demonstrated significant diastolic dysfunction and congestion, including elevated filling pressures and enlarged left atrial volumes. In this setting, chronic characteristics such as age and comorbidities likely influenced long-term prognosis rather than short-term outcomes. Acute biomarkers such as NT-proBNP appear better suited to reflect the active pathophysiological processes driving clinical deterioration during hospitalization. Similar observations were reported by Tan and colleagues from Singapore in 2024, who showed that natriuretic peptides remain closely linked to cardiac structure, congestion, and prognosis regardless of ejection fraction.¹¹

A steady rise in 30-day readmission rates was observed across increasing NT-proBNP levels. Patients with lower values were less likely to require early rehospitalization, whereas nearly half of those with NT-proBNP levels exceeding 10,000 pg/mL were readmitted within one month of discharge. Although this trend narrowly missed statistical significance, it is clinically meaningful. Elevated NT-proBNP at admission likely reflects unresolved congestion, persistent neurohormonal activation, or limited physiological reserve, which may persist beyond discharge despite apparent clinical improvement. As a result, discharge may represent symptomatic stabilization rather than complete resolution of underlying disease. Similar findings were reported by Kaler and colleagues in Indonesia in 2024, who identified higher natriuretic peptide levels as predictors of early rehospitalization and adverse cardiovascular outcomes [4,9].^{12,16}

The association between NT-proBNP and illness complexity was further supported by its relationship with length of hospital stay. Patients with higher NT-proBNP levels required longer inpatient care, likely reflecting delayed stabilization and the need for more intensive therapy. Harshitha and colleagues from India in 2025 reported comparable results, demonstrating a positive correlation between NT-proBNP levels and duration of hospitalization in heart failure patients.¹⁰ These findings reinforce the role of NT-proBNP as an indicator of overall disease burden rather than a marker of mortality alone.

In-hospital mortality also increased progressively with higher NT-proBNP levels. Patients with markedly elevated NT-proBNP experienced higher mortality rates compared with those in lower categories. While statistical significance was not achieved, likely due to the limited number of deaths, the direction of this association is consistent with prior studies.¹³ Andrews and colleagues from the United States in 2025 demonstrated that baseline NT-proBNP strongly predicted survival, functional status, and quality-of-life outcomes, highlighting its ability to capture cumulative myocardial stress and reduced physiological reserve.⁹ Similar observations were made by Cristescu and colleagues from Romania

in 2025, who showed that elevated NT-proBNP was associated with increased in-hospital mortality, particularly when accompanied by systemic illness.¹⁴

Traditional risk factors, including age, sex, diabetes, hypertension, atrial fibrillation, and ischemic heart disease, were not independently associated with short-term outcomes in this data set. This suggests that, during acute hospitalization, immediate hemodynamic and neurohormonal stress may outweigh the influence of chronic comorbidities. Although sex-based differences in natriuretic peptide prognostic value have been reported in larger cohorts, as shown by Bobrowski and colleagues from Canada in 2025, such effects may be less evident in short-term analyses with limited sample sizes.¹⁵ Additionally, findings by Hong and colleagues from South Korea in 2023 demonstrated that elevated natriuretic peptide levels are associated with poor outcomes across diverse acute cardiac conditions, supporting their role as markers of global cardiac stress rather than disease-specific indicators.¹³

Overall, these findings suggest that NT-proBNP behaves as a continuous marker of disease severity in acute decompensated heart failure. Even in the absence of statistically significant associations, the consistent and biologically plausible trends observed across readmission, length of stay, and mortality outcomes highlight its clinical relevance.¹⁶ Measurement of NT-

proBNP at admission may therefore aid early risk stratification, identify patients requiring closer monitoring or intensified management, and support discharge planning aimed at reducing early adverse outcomes.

LIMITATIONS

This study has a few important limitations. Being conducted at a single center, the findings may not fully reflect outcomes in other settings. The number of in-hospital deaths was relatively small, which may have limited the ability to detect statistically significant associations. NT-proBNP was assessed only at admission, and changes during hospitalization were not evaluated. Information on inpatient treatment intensity, medication optimization, and post-discharge follow-up was also limited and may have influenced outcomes. As with all observational studies, the findings describe associations and should not be interpreted as causal.

CONCLUSION

Patients admitted with higher NT-proBNP levels tended to have poorer short-term outcomes, including more frequent readmissions and higher in-hospital mortality. These findings suggest that NT-proBNP measured at admission provides a useful snapshot of disease severity and can help guide early clinical decision-making and discharge planning in acute heart failure.

Table 1: Distribution of baseline characteristics among the study participants.

Variables	n (%)
Age	
18 to 50 years	03 (1.6)
51 to 85 years	187 (98.4)
Gender	
Male	62 (32.6)
Female	128 (67.4)
Diabetes Mellitus	
Yes	152 (80)
No	38 (20)
Hypertension	
Yes	170 (89.5)
No	20 (10.5)

Atrial fibrillation	
Yes	31 (16.3)
No	159 (62.1)
Ischemic heart disease	
Yes	72 (37.9)
No	118 (62.1)
SGLT2 use	
Yes	22 (11.6)
No	168 (88.4)
Level of NT-pro BNP	
<1500	75 (39.5)
1500-5000	61 (32.1)
5001-10000	25 (13.2)
>10000	29 (15.3)
30 day Readmission	
Yes	66 (34.7)
No	124 (65.3)
In-hospital mortality	
Yes	19 (10)
No	171 (90)
Total	190 (100)

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of continuous variables.

Variables	Mean±SD
Age (Years)	71.07±11.45
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.25±6.22
Creatinine (mg/dl)	1.79±1.22
HbA1c	6.87±1.58
E/e ratio	18.70±6.61
PASP	36.54±16.14
EF	57.87±2.91
LAVI	40.46±14.86
LVDD	1.29±0.83
Length of hospital stay	5.20±3.57

Table 3: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the 30 day Readmission groups.

Variables	Readmission Yes n (%)	Readmission No n (%)	P value
Age 18 to 50 years 51 to 85 years	00 (00) 66 (35.3)	03 (100) 121 (64.7)	0.20
Gender Male Female	27 (43.5) 39 (30.5)	35 (56.5) 89 (69.5)	0.07
Diabetes Mellitus Yes No	56 (36.8) 10 (26.3)	96 (63.2) 28 (73.7)	0.22
Hypertension Yes No	56 (32.9) 10 (50)	114 (67.1) 10 (50)	0.13
Atrial fibrillation Yes No	11 (35.5) 55 (34.6)	20 (64.5) 104 (65.4)	0.92
Ischemic heart disease Yes No	25 (34.7) 41 (34.7)	47 (65.3) 77 (65.3)	0.99
SGLT2 use Yes No	06 (27.3) 60 (35.7)	16 (72.7) 108 (64.3)	0.43
Level of NT-pro BNP <1500 1500-5000 5001-10000 >10000	18 (24) 23 (37.7) 11 (44) 14 (48.3)	57 (76) 38 (62.3) 14 (56) 15 (51.7)	0.06

Table 4: Distribution of patient characteristics according to the in-hospital mortality groups.

Variables	In-hospital admission Yes n (%)	In-hospital admission No n (%)	P value
Age 18 to 50 years 51 to 85 years	00 (00) 19 (10.2)	03 (100) 168 (89.8)	0.56
Gender Male Female	09 (14.5) 10 (7.8)	53 (85.5) 118 (92.2)	0.14
Diabetes Mellitus Yes No	16 (10.5) 03 (7.9)	136 (89.5) 35 (92.1)	0.62
Hypertension Yes No	16 (9.4) 03 (15)	154 (90.6) 17 (85)	0.43
Atrial fibrillation Yes No	05 (16.1) 14 (8.8)	26 (83.9) 145 (91.2)	0.21
Ischemic heart disease Yes No	10 (13.9) 09 (7.6)	62 (86.1) 109 (92.4)	0.16
SGLT2 use Yes No	00 (00) 19 (11.3)	22 (100) 149 (88.7)	0.09
Level of NT-pro BNP <1500 1500-5000 5001-10000 >10000	06 (8) 05 (8.2) 03 (12) 05 (17.2)	69 (92) 56 (91.8) 22 (88) 24 (82.8)	0.50

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